

Social

ATTITUDE TOWARDS TEACHER ELIGIBILITY TEST AMONG BED TRAINEES

G. Sorna Lakshmi ^{*1}, Dr.M.Leonard Ashok ²

^{*1} MSc., MPhil., Med, Assistant Professor in Biological Science, PadmaShree College of Education, India

² Principal, CMS College of Education, Coimbatore, India

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Abstract

Teacher Eligibility Test known as TET is an Indian entrance examination for teachers. The test is conducted by both Central government and State governments in India. The test is conducted in order to fulfill the achieve Right to education goals. After passing the teacher eligibility test only teachers will be selected for the government services. Even most of the teachers are against teacher eligibility test. The present study will plan to know the views & attitude towards teacher eligibility test among the school teachers. Attitude is simply defined as views, opinions, ideas, feelings, fears, towards particular event. This paper is an attempt to find the Attitude towards teacher eligibility test among BEd trainees. In the present study survey method was used. The investigator adopted the survey method to study the attitude of BEd trainees towards teacher eligibility test. Investigators selected only 300 BEd trainees as sample in Coimbatore district using stratified random sampling. The findings reveal that there is a moderate attitude towards teacher eligibility test among the selected BEd trainees in Coimbatore district.

Keywords: Attitude; Teacher Eligibility Test.

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1. Introduction

Qualifying in a Teacher Eligibility Test (TET) is now mandatory for all existing and aspiring primary and middle school teachers in the country, with the passing of the Right to Education Act. The National Council of Teacher Education (NCTE) has published the guidelines for conducting the TET, providing complete details about rationale for the test, eligibility to take the test, the structure and syllabus for the test, the type of questions that would be asked and the marks required to qualify as a teacher.

To be eligible to take the CTET or any other TET conducted by the states, one has to have a degree or diploma in education (BEd or D. Ed) or be on the verge of completing a degree in the year of taking the test. Teachers will need to take the TET within a period of 5 years from the time the TET is first notified. This kind of a qualifying test can help improve the quality of teachers right from the recruitment stage.

The Central Government and many States have begun conducting the TET. The Central Teacher Eligibility Test (CTET) was conducted by the CBSE for the first time in June 2011. The next CTET will be held on January 29, 2012.

It had been inter alia provided that one of the essential qualifications for a person to be eligible for appointment as a teacher in any of the schools referred to in clause (n) of section 2 of the Right To Education Act is that he/ she should pass the Teacher Eligibility Test (TET) which will be conducted by the appropriate Government in accordance with the Guidelines framed by the NCTE.

The rationale for including the TET as a minimum qualification for a person to be eligible for appointment as a teacher is as under:

- It would bring national standards and benchmark of teacher quality in the recruitment process.
- It would induce teacher education institutions and students from these institutions to further improve their performance standards.
- It would send a positive signal to all stakeholders that the Government lays special emphasis on teacher quality.

2. Origin of TET EXAM

Cooch Behar (WB): The process for the Teachers Eligibility Test for recruitment of primary school teachers has been initiated in Cooch Behar district. The authorities of the District Primary School Council (DPSC) and the Uttar Banga Kshetriya Garmin Bank reached an agreement in this regard on Wednesday evening. The matter is now under consideration of the District Magistrate for his approval. DPSC chairperson Kalyani Poddar said today that the application forms for the TET will be distributed from the selected 35 branches of the Garmin Bank on and from November 17. The forms will arrive in Cooch Behar from Kolkata within a day or two, Poddar said. The DPSC chairperson also said that the TET examination will be held on the same day all over the state. After the completion of the TET examination, the DPSC will be able to fill up vacant posts of teachers in the primary schools.

3. Teaching Aptitude Tests in India

The national commission on teachers (i) 1983-85 has very rightly lamented the absence of measuring teaching aptitude while selecting teachers. It said, “our feelings is that in the absence of reliable tests of general ability and aptitude for teaching, in the most places there has been a tendency to go primarily by the qualification of the candidates as recorded in certificates”.

An NCERT publication entitled, tools for BEd admission has stressed the important of selecting right types of teachers on some reliable criteria. The criteria could include (a) Aptitude test, (b) Teacher trait test, (c) Teaching efficiency inventories, (d) Teaching attitude test, and (e) Tests of intelligence and general mental ability.

A perusal of the existing literature on teacher/teaching aptitude tests reveals that only seven aptitude tests have been constructed in India.

- 1) Jai parkas' teaching aptitude test, containing 150 items.
- 2) M.M. Shah's teaching aptitude test, 1962 includes 120 items.
- 3) 3 .R. P.Srivastava's teaching aptitude test, 1965 comprises 15 statements.
- 4) K.P. Panddey's teaching aptitude test, 1968.
- 5) S.N. Sharma's teaching aptitude test, 1969 consisting of 120 items.
- 6) B. M. Upadhaya's teaching aptitude test, 1976 has 125 items.
- 7) D.P. Patel's teaching aptitude test, 1980 includes 152 items.

Teacher's aptitude test usually includes items and statements under these heads:1. Mental ability. 2. Attitude towards children.3. Interest in the profession. 4. Attitude towards community. 5. Skills in teaching.6. Interest in reading. 7. Reading comprehension. 8. Number skills.9. General information (Agarwall 2007).

HYPOTHESIS: 1

There will be a significant mean score difference in the attitude towards teacher eligibility test between Govt and Private college selected B.Ed, trainees.

Table: 1 Mean score difference and t-ratio of attitude towards teacher eligibility test between the Govt and Private college selected B.Ed trainees

Factors	Group	N	Mean	S.D	df	t-value	p-value	Result
Cognitive	Govt	111	40.23	6.031	313	0.239	0.811	N.S
	private	204	40.07	5.000				
Affective	Govt	111	22.59	4.434	313	-1.362	0.174	N.S
	private	204	23.32	4.548				
Conation	Govt	111	29.23	4.882	313	-0.598	0.550	N.S
	private	204	29.55	4.419				
Evaluation	Govt	111	12.05	3.465	313	-0.691	0.490	N.S
	private	204	12.32	3.393				
Total	Govt	111	104.09	12.636	313	-0.824	0.411	N.S
	private	204	105.26	11.785				

The **Table 1** shows that mean score difference in attitude towards teacher eligibility test between government and private selected B.Ed. College students. According to the table t-value is statistically not significant at 0.05 levels for all the factor. However, in total the attitude towards teacher eligibility test is statistically not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the hypothesis 1 rejected and it can be concluded that there is no significant difference in attitude towards teacher eligibility test between government and private B.Ed. students.

Chart 1:

HYPOTHESIS: 2

There will be a significant mean score difference in attitude towards teacher eligibility test between Tamil and English medium selected B.Ed, trainees.

Table: 2 Mean score difference and t-ratio of attitude towards teacher eligibility test between Tamil and English medium selected B.Ed, trainees

Factors	Group	N	Mean	S.D	df	t-value	p-value	Result
Cognitive	Tamil	159	40.81	5.447	313	2.296	0.022	S
	English	156	39.43	5.230				
Affective	Tamil	159	23.50	4.166	313	1.726	0.085	S
	English	156	22.62	4.817				
Conation	Tamil	159	29.35	4.537	313	0.323	0.745	N.S
	English	156	29.52	4.641				

Evaluation	Tamil	159	12.78	3.412	313	2,944	0.003	S
	English	156	11.66	3.336				
Total	Tamil	159	106.44	11.733	313	2,374	0.018	S
	English	156	103.23	12.259				

The **Table 2** shows that mean score difference in attitude towards teacher eligibility test between Tamil and English medium selected B.Ed, trainees. According to the table t-value is statistically not significant at 0.05 levels for conation factor and statistically significant at 0.05 levels for the cognitive, affective, and evaluation factors. However, in total attitudes towards teacher eligibility test is statistically significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the hypothesis 2 is accepted and it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in attitude towards teacher eligibility test between Tamil and English medium selected B.Ed, Students.

CHART 2:

Conclusion

It is found that there is a significant difference in attitude towards teacher eligibility test between Tamil and English medium selected B.Ed, trainees. Tamil medium students possess better

attitude than English medium students. This may be because in Tamil Nadu Government teacher recruitment, tamil medium students are given more preferences.

References

- [1] Divye Walwani 2012, Kailash Chaudhary completes his research on Teachers personality. Published: June 5, 2012 |
- [2] Dr Sandhya Mehta,(2012). International journal of business and management tomorrow. international journal of business and management tomorrow vol. 2 no. 2
- [3] Golden, S. A. R. (2011). Problems and Prospectus of Distance Education. Quality Enhancement In Distance Education For Life Long Learning, 1(1), 343-344.
- [4] Golden, S. A. R. (2016). RURAL STUDENTS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS ENGLISH AS MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTION IN HIGHER EDUCATION – AN ANALYSIS. International Journal of Research, 3(Special Issue - 16), 1-10.
- [5] Golden, S. A. R. (2017). Attitude of Students and Teachers towards E- Learning - An Analysis. Recent Research in Social Science & Humanities, 1, 5-10.
- [6] Golden, S. A. R. (2017). Recent Research In Social Science & Humanities.
- [7] Jenelle R. Reeves, Secondary Teacher Attitudes toward Including English-Language Learners in Mainstream Classrooms.
- [8] Olufemi Aremu Fakolade, Samuel Olufemi Adeniyi, Adeyinka Tella, Attitude of teachers towards the inclusion of special needs children in general education classroom: the case of teachers in some selected schools in Nigeria. Vol.1, Issue 3, June, 2009.ISSN:1307-9298.
- [9] Patricia Garcia, Ed.D, Lori Kupczynski, Ed.D, Glenda Holland, ED.D, 2011. Impact of Teacher Personality Styles on Academic Excellence of Secondary Students. National forum of teacher education journal volume 21, number 3, 201.
- [10] Syed Shafqat Ali Shah, impact of teacher's behaviour on the academic achievement of university students 2009.